

A Thermodynamic Study of Some Tetracyclines and Their Complexes with Indium(III) in Aqueous Medium

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Thermodynamic parameters of protonated tetracycline, oxytetracycline, chlorotetracycline and dimethylchlorotetracycline and their complexes with In(III) were determined. The changes in ΔH° and ΔS° have indicated that (a) the nature of linkage of the dissociating proton of the tricarbonylmethane system must be somewhat different from that of the phenol- β -diketone system and of the dimethylammonium cation, in solution and (b) the contact of the phenolic oxygen at C_{10} with metal ion is electrostatic in nature and the ketonic oxygen at C_{11} is attached to the metal ion with covalent forces.

The reversible half-wave potential of simple In(III) ion, which can not be measured directly owing to the irreversible nature of the reduction, was calculated as -500.2 ± 0.2 , -491.7 ± 0.2 and -483.4 ± 0.3 mV vs SCE at 20, 30 and 40°, respectively.

TETRACYCLINES are a family of broad-spectrum antibiotics of known prophylactic and therapeutic values. They form strong coordination complexes with metal ions^{1,2}. The antibacterial activity is approximately the same³ but its mechanism has not been definitely established, though it is believed to be associated with the formation of mixed complexes of antibiotic, ribosomes and a metal ion⁴. These findings have stimulated work on the behaviour of tetracyclines with metal ions.

In this paper, the thermodynamic data for tetracycline (TC), oxytetracycline (OTC), chlorotetracycline (CTC) and dimethylchlorotetracycline (DMCTC) and their complexes with In(III) have been reported. With the help of these data, the nature of the bonds between the dissociating protons and their related oxygen atoms, and between the metal ion and the antibiotic molecules has been discussed.

Experimental

Reagents: TC, CTC and DMCTC were obtained from the Cyanamid India, Limited (Ledereley Division) as hydrochlorides and used as such. Clinical grade OTC-HCl, purified by crystallization from methanol in the form of needles, m.p. 189-196° (decomposition), was used. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. Fresh solutions prepared in redistilled water were always used to avoid decomposition of the antibiotics. NaClO₄ and gelatin were used as supporting electrolyte and maxima suppressor, respectively. Purified nitrogen was used for the removal of oxygen.

Apparatus: Current-potential curves were recorded with a manual polarograph described

earlier⁵, using a capillary having a flow rate of 1.86 mg/sec of mercury and a drop time of 3.47 sec/drop at 43.24 cm corrected height (h_{corr}) of mercury column in 0.1 M NaClO₄ solution in open circuit. pH measurements were made with ECIL pH-meter (pH-823).

Procedures: The successive dissociation constants pK_a^H , pK_a^H and pK_a^H of protonated tetracyclines were determined by the pH-titration technique of Irving and Rossotti⁶, from the pH vs degree of formation of proton-antibiotic complexes (\bar{n}_A) curves, corresponding to the values of \bar{n}_A at 2.5, 1.5 and 0.5, respectively.

For the determination of stability constants of the complexes, the half-wave potentials of In(III) were measured in presence of $5 \times 10^{-3}\%$ gelatin at ionic strength of 0.1 M (maintained by the addition of requisite amount of NaClO₄) in two ways, (a) at constant antibiotic concentration (0.01 M) in the pH range of 1.00 to 4.70 and (b) at constant pH values between 2.80 and 3.40 (all ± 0.01) and varying concentration of the antibiotics (0.5-100 mM). The measurements were made separately at 20, 30 and 40° (all $\pm 0.5^\circ$). The values of stability constants were then calculated by the method of Momoki and Ogawa⁷ with the aid of shift in the half-wave potential with respect to $[LH^-]$, where LH_3^+ represents the protonated antibiotic cation, using the following equation:

$$E'_o[X] = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{F}{2.303RT} \{E_{1/2(m)} - E_{1/2(o)}\} + \log \frac{i_{d(m)}}{i_{d(o)}} \right] \quad \dots (i)$$

$$= \beta'_o + \beta'_1[X] + \beta'_2[X]^2 + \dots \quad \dots (ii)$$

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TABLE 1—SUCCESSIVE DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF PROTONATED TETRACYCLINES AND OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES WITH In(III) ($\mu=0.1 M$)

	TC			OTC			OTC			DMCTC		
	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°
pK_1^H	3.55	3.52	3.49	3.38	3.36	3.34	3.42	3.40	3.38	3.60	3.57	3.54
pK_2^H	7.40	7.27	7.14	7.30	7.18	7.06	7.20	7.08	6.97	7.02	6.90	6.79
pK_3^H	8.96	8.80	8.65	8.55	8.40	8.26	8.59	8.44	8.30	8.86	8.70	8.55
$\log \beta_1$	8.65	8.52	8.40	8.54	8.41	8.29	8.45	8.33	8.22	8.31	8.20	8.10
$\log \beta_2$	15.11	14.84	14.59	14.83	14.57	14.33	14.74	14.49	14.26	14.63	14.40	14.19
$\log K_s$	6.46	6.32	6.19	6.29	6.16	6.04	6.29	6.16	6.04	6.32	6.20	6.09

where $F'_0[X]$ is an experimentally determinable Momoki-Ogawa function at $[X]=[LH^-]$ and is related to apparent stability constants $\beta'_0, \beta'_1, \beta'_2, \dots$ by eq. (ii); n, R, F and T have their usual significance; $E_{1/2(m)}$ and $i_{d(m)}$ are the half-wave potential and diffusion current respectively of complexed ion at any value of $[X]=m$ where the system 'would be' reversible and $E_{1/2(e)}$ and $i_{d(e)}$ are respectively the corresponding values of complexed ion at any value of $[X]>m$. By plotting $F_1[X]$ vs $[X]$, the apparent successive stability constants of the complexes, β'_j , can be analysed. The successive stability constants may, then, be calculated using eq. (iii):

$$\beta_j = \beta'_j / \beta'_0 \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

The thermodynamic functions were calculated in the usual way.

Results and Discussion

An extended and ill-defined polarographic wave of irreversible nature was obtained for the reduction of In(III) in presence of 0.1 M NaClO₄ and 5 × 10⁻³% gelatin at all temperatures. Our result, with respect to this reduction, is in agreement with previous reports⁹⁻¹². But in the presence of TC, OTC, CTC and DMCTC, In(III) produced a well-defined reversible wave. The log plots analyses gave straight lines with reciprocal slopes of 20 ± 1.2 mV, which are in good agreement with the theoretical value for a reversible three electron reduction. The plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}_{corr}$ gave straight lines passing through the origin indicating entirely diffusion-controlled reduction processes.

The temperature coefficient of the diffusion current was found to be 1.02 ± 0.03%/degree with a temperature variation from 20 to 40°. This is consistent with a diffusion-controlled reversible electrode process. The value of half-wave potential became less negative with an increase in temperature and the value of $dE_{1/2}/dT$ was found to be 1 ± 0.05 mV/degree. This positive temperature coefficient of $E_{1/2}$ indicates that an appreciable activation energy is required in the electrode reaction for the reduction of hydrated In(III) ions.

Successive stability constants: The half-wave potentials plotted against $-\log [LH^-]$ (obtained from the pH studies at constant antibiotic concentration

and the antibiotic concentration studies at constant pH , using pH of solution and pK_a^H and amount of each antibiotic) fall on the same smooth curve in each system. This result indicates that (a) more than one complex species are present in each system, (b) the role of pH on these systems is simply to change the concentration of the various (protonated and deprotonated) species of antibiotics, (c) the hydroxyl ions are not taking part in the reduction processes and (d) the reducing species are only the metal-aquo-antibiotic complexes.

Because of the irreversible reduction of simple In(III) ion and its reversible reduction in presence of antibiotics, the successive stability constants were calculated by the method of Momoki and Ogawa⁷. The plots of $F'_2[X]$ vs $[X]$ were parallel to the $[X]$ axis for all the systems indicating the formation of two complexes with metal to ligand ratios of 1:1 and 1:2. The values of stability constants for all the complexes are presented in Table 1.

Higher complexes may exist but could not be identified due to hydrolysis at higher pH .

Half-wave potential of simple In(III) ion: The reversible half-wave potential of simple In(III) ion was calculated by using eq. (iv)

$$E_{1/2(e)} = E_{1/2(m)} - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \beta'_0 \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

at all the temperatures with the assumption that $i_{d(m)}$ is equal to the diffusion current of the simple metal ion in the same medium. The values so obtained are -500.2 ± 0.2 , -491.7 ± 0.2 and -483.4 ± 0.3 mV vs SCE at 20, 30 and 40°, respectively, which are in good agreement with those in literature (e.g., 497 ± 0.3 mV⁷, 521.3 mV⁸, 503.0 mV⁹, 483.3 mV¹⁰ and 485.0 mV¹¹).

Thermodynamics of the ligands and their complexes:

The average of calculated values of thermodynamic functions of tetracyclines for the deprotonation reactions, I-III are given in Table 2

The values of ΔH° for the first deprotonation are much less negative than those for the second and the third deprotonation reactions. Consequently, the nature of linkage of the dissociating proton of the tricarbonylmethane system in aqueous medium must be somewhat different from those of the phenyl- β -diketone system and the dimethylammonium cation. From the viewpoint of existence of keto-enol equilibrium in tricarbonylmethane system to form two isomers^{1,2}, the reason for this probably may be the presence of more electrovalent forces than covalent forces between the O and H atoms of C₃, while covalent forces, rather than electrovalent forces, are dominating in the phenol- β -diketone system and in the dimethylammonium group between O and H atoms at C₁₀ and between N and H atoms at C₄, respectively.

The thermodynamic functions of the complexation reactions (IV-V),

and

where $K_1 = \beta_1$ and $K_1 \cdot K_2 = \beta_2$, were calculated from the stability constants and are also presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS* FOR DEPROTONATION OF TETRACYCLINES AND THEIR COMPLEXES WITH In(III) ($\mu = 0.1 M$)

	TC	OTC	CTC	DMCTC
For deprotonation				
ΔH_1°	5.27	3.52	3.52	5.27
ΔH_2°	22.8	21.1	20.2	20.2
ΔH_3°	27.2	25.5	25.5	27.2
ΔS_1°	50.0	52.7	58.5	50.9
ΔS_2°	63.7	67.8	68.9	65.5
ΔS_3°	78.7	76.8	77.5	76.7
For Complexation				
ΔH_1°	21.9	21.9	20.2	18.4
ΔH_2°	23.7	21.9	21.9	20.2
$\Delta H_{\beta_1}^\circ$	45.6	43.9	42.1	38.2
ΔS_1°	90.7	88.6	92.9	96.2
ΔS_2°	42.8	45.5	45.5	52.1
$\Delta S_{\beta_2}^\circ$	133.5	134.1	138.4	148.3

* Values of ΔH° and ΔS° have units of k.J. mole⁻¹ and J.^ok⁻¹. mole⁻¹, respectively.

An examination of the ΔH° and ΔS° values of the complexes of the same metal to ligand ratios shows that these are very close to each other indicating the presence of similar binding properties in them. The higher stability for the formation of 1:1 complex is essentially an entropy effect since

$\Delta S_1^\circ - \Delta S_2^\circ$ is always positive and is approximately equal to ΔS_3° , and ΔH° for both type of complexes are approximately the same.

In general, the value of ΔH_2° is more negative than that of ΔH_1° for all the systems. This suggests that the coordination of the first molecule of the antibiotic with the metal ion may result in a weakening of the remaining metal-water bonds in the complexes and additional release of water molecules from the metal ion in the formation of the $\text{In}(\text{LH})_2^{2+}$ species compared to the formation of $\text{In}(\text{LH})_2^+$ complex.

Due to the facts that (a) the ion pair formation between the metal ion and charged donor atoms is accompanied by positive ΔS° and by zero (or positive) ΔH° values^{14,15}, (b) the net entropy change is small if the donor atom is neutral in charge, while it may be more positive with charged donor atoms^{16,17} and (c) the negatively charged oxygen atom of the phenolic group at C₁₀ and ketonic oxygen atom at C₁₁ coordinate with metal ions to form one or two six-membered chelate ring/s for the complexation^{1,2}, we may conclude that the contact of the phenolic oxygen atom at C₁₀ with In(III) ion is primarily electrostatic in nature and is responsible for the positive ΔS° values, and that the ketonic oxygen atom at C₁₁ is attached to the metal ion with covalent forces and contributes negative ΔH° values.

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